

FORMATION OF IDEAS ABOUT MEASURING DIFFERENT SIZES USING CONDITIONAL MEASUREMENT IN CHILDREN

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Annotation. This article analyzes the methods of forming visions of measuring different sizes in children using conditional measurement.

Keywords: measurement, conditional measurement, length measurement, weight measurement, fluid measurement.

Perception and comparison of the size of objects. Before teaching children conditional measurements, it is necessary to explain the following rules that will help the accurate output of the measurement:

1. The pill is always about starting the measurement from the very edge.
2. On the need to mark the end of the scale.
3. When measuring the length of the object, the measurement is taken from left to ten, and the time when measuring the height with the width is taken from top to bottom.
4. About the fact that the next measurement should be started from the place where the last mark was placed.
5. About the fact that at the time of taking the measure, one should definitely count its number.

When teaching children to measure length, it is proposed to measure the length of the ribbons or draw a frame on the stripes, depending on the number of measurements.

Children do not have much difficulty at the time of obtaining the dimensions of the finished objects, as opposed to taking the dimensions of the objects in the picture. Therefore, ready-made objects should be used when teaching children to get the right size. Also a certain number of measurements should not be numerous, i.e. 5-6.

During special activities carried out in everyday life, children learn different ways to measure length. It is enough just to explain to the children at the time of training to measure the width that the measurement is placed in the transverse direction of the subject. The skills acquired during the measurement of the length and width of the object are applied during the measurement of height, so they do not have difficulty obtaining this measurement and begin to take the measurement correctly at the first training session.

Experiments and observations have shown that children aged 6-7 years have the ability to fully master the measurement of length.

How do children understand weight size? Observation and children's response show that children 6-7 years old know that weight should be measured through scales.

When asked how much sugar is in bags (bags), the children answer "it needs to be weighed".

They also give answers to this question that express the domestic home experience. For example: "it is necessary to measure with a glass". Children do not know that the weight

of these things is his stone. The stones are large and small, heavy and light. If children's knowledge of length and weight is compared, we make sure they have a lot of weight knowledge. Children's knowledge of fluid capacity has been found to be very low. Most children do not know how to measure the milk in the jug. They are answered with a "centimeter", with a liner, with a gradusnik. Children's responses indicate that they have no knowledge of measuring fluids, scattering bodies. Children do not know the rules for measuring liquids, what is the size of the liquid. In children's stories, they say that they received a liter of milk with their mothers, but they do not know that liters are the unit of measurement of liquids. Teaching to measure different things greatly affects the mental progress of the child. Therefore, as a result of the kindergarten's training in large preparatory groups, it is necessary to measure the length, measure the weight, measure the capacity of liquids and familiarize them with their units of measurement.

As a result of teaching:

1. Measurement gives the child accurate knowledge of the object being measured.
2. The number of measurements will depend on whether it is large or small.
3. Indicates that there is a functional relationship between the number of measurements and their size.

Thus, children's knowledge of conditional measure leads to an extension of their knowledge of general measure.

Game to strengthen knowledge: "near - far".

Game Rule: 4 types: close, close, longer, long distance baskets are made. Children are lined up on two sides in two rows.

A child from each row comes to the distance told by the tutor, and the ball must be thrown into the basket at the distance told by the tutor. At what distance the ball falls, the children say that distance is close, far, closer, farther away, and give the turn to the next child. The game can be repeated 2-3 times, continuing in this way.

As a result of the exercise, the child understands the words "close" and "long" and correctly applies it in speech.

Educator: children, now you take the shape of a circle from the box next to you. Place this shape relatively far away from you (on the table). Now place the square shape relatively close to you. Take the shape of a triangle and place it closer to yourself. Place the rectangular shape further away. The educator observed the work of the children "is the Circle far from you close?", "Is the Triangle away from you, closer?" he asks.

The magic sack game.

The children stand in a circle, the tutor stands in the middle of the circle, the tutor has a "magic pouch" in his hand, the pouch contains fabrics of different thicknesses and lengths, pencils. Children come one by one and hold something from the bag and tell what it is and how it is, and take it out of the bag and tell it its color. Items that children find correctly are seized.

Understands the words "close" and "long" and correctly applies in speech. Revealing the possibilities and specifics of preschool children to master the concept of the large-small size of things as a result of scientific examinations makes it possible to determine the necessary amount of knowledge and qualifications that are needed by the department given in the program for each young Gruppe in kindergarten. Great importance is attached to organizing quantitative observations of everything around, how children use knowledge and skills of

mathematical content in different types of their activities. In educational activities and in everyday life, didactic games and play-exercises are widely used. In addition to educational activities, by organizing games, the mathematical imagination of children is strengthened, deepened and expanded. In educational activities, the active activity of children is primarily ensured by working on a new material and correctly adding together the repetition of the previously mentioned material, alternating types of work and methods of its organization, that is, the structure of educational activities..

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